

Studying the influence of milk processing on two relaxation components of aged cheeses through benchtop FFC-NMR analysis[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Hard PDO (Protected designation of origin) cheeses such as Parmigiano Reggiano or Fiore Sardo are traditionally made with raw milk, as this allows them to develop their characteristic texture, taste, and smell. Guidelines for the Fiore Sardo production mandate that it should be made from raw milk, but industrial products have been long suspected of being produced using pasteurized or thermized milk. Concerning quality control of the non-bovine milk dairy products, there is no official, reliable, and fast method to differentiate between raw milk and pasteurized milk cheeses. In this work, we present benchtop Fast Field Cycling-Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (FFC-NMR) relaxometry as a possible method for such discrimination. Beyond being the yes or no technique, it allows a deep characterization of the molecular dynamic of cheese components, describing the state of the water, fat, and protein matrix. In this work, we demonstrate that using a new FFC-NMR approach, the protons within Fiore Sardo cheeses can be grouped into two populations, characterized by short and long NMR relaxation times, respectively. With this result, we demonstrate that the artisanal and industrial cheeses can be uniquely identified and that the component with short relaxation time is a good indicator to discriminate them. As far as we know, this innovative approach has never been used to study food products.

1. Introduction

Dairy consumption dates back at least 6000 years. Nowadays, it is a large market that is growing each year with new products and innovative approaches to the production and control of dairy products. However, many traditional dairy products are still produced according to the traditional processes to keep their nutritional and sensorial characteristics unaltered.

One of the main products in the dairy sector is cheese. The European Union is the world's largest cheese producer with a wide variety of cheeses, and Italy is among the largest producers of hard cheeses in Europe. (Cheese | USDA Foreign Agricultural Service, 2024).

Milk, as the main raw material of dairy products, greatly influences the quality of end products. The composition of milk consists of micellar and soluble globular proteins (mainly caseins and lactoglobulins), fat

globules, and water (plus other minor components such as vitamins, minerals, and lactose). Several processing operations can be carried out to transform raw milk into cheese. Changes in the composition and molecular structure of raw milk play a significant role in determining the quality, texture, and evolution during the aging of cheese, which in turn influence sensory properties (e.g. creaminess, elasticity, firmness, graininess, odor and taste).

Nowadays, many cheeses are produced from pasteurized milk. Nevertheless, some well-known and economically relevant PDO (Protected designation of origin) European cheeses (e.g. Parmigiano Reggiano PDO, Grana Padano PDO, Roquefort PDO, Camembert de Normandie PDO, Queso Manchego Artesano PDO, Gruyere PDO), must be manufactured exclusively from raw milk. The use of raw milk is often linked to artisanal, traditional dairy products strongly rooted in the territories of origin and characterized by a relevant cultural and

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historical meaning.

Raw milk, as defined in the Code of Hygienic Practice for Milk and Milk Products (CAC/RCP 57–2004) and EU regulation (*Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 of 29 April 2004, Laying down specific hygiene rules for the hygiene of foodstuffs, Annex I, 2004*), is milk that has not been heated beyond 40 °C or undergone any treatment that has an equivalent effect.

Heat treatment of milk is used to reduce the number of pathogenic microorganisms. However, by thermal treatment, desirable lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are also reduced, and other structural changes occur, which influence, to an extent that is proportional to the severity of the heat treatment, milk quality and functionality (Samelis et al., 2009; Singh & Waungana, 2001).

Fiore Sardo PDO cheese production dates back to the Bronze Age. It must be produced according to the original cheesemaking protocol (*Regulation - 1263/96 - EN - EUR-LEX, 2025*) from raw whole sheep milk. After coagulation with lamb rennet paste at 34 °C < T < 36 °C and syneresis, curd is kept uncooked, salted, smoked, and ripened for at least 105 days. In the last decades, industrial production of Fiore Sardo cheese has been mainly obtained by a few industrial producers, the share of industrial Fiore Sardo reaching up to over 90 % of the total annual production. In 2022, a significant batch of industrial Fiore Sardo cheeses (almost 700 tons) was seized from the market due to suspicions that it had been produced from pasteurized milk, in violation of the guidelines set forth by the production specifications, which mandate that Fiore Sardo be made from raw milk. In contrast, small-scale artisans produce the Fiore Sardo following the traditional method, using raw milk. The debate over the need to safeguard the traditional production of Fiore Sardo versus the possibility to produce it using pasteurized or thermized milk is very active (Caboni et al., 2019; Mulas et al., 2013; Sardinia Regional Council Question N. 1380 A, 2018, Sardinia Regional Council Question N. 1706 A, 2018; Siniscalchi, 2013; Siniscalchi, 2014).

However, assessing differences between cheeses made with processed and non-processed milk is a complex and non-straightforward task. Moreover, currently, there is no direct way to verify if the milk used for ewe cheese manufacture underwent any kind of pre-processing treatment (Rankin et al., 2010).

Most of the methods used for quality control testing of dairy products are microbial or chemical tests, which require excessive sample preparation and are labor- and time-consuming. Some frequently used tests require 24–48 h to perform, making them unsuitable for the production environment (Kraggerud, 2011).

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) is a non-invasive, non-destructive technique that is becoming increasingly used for quality control in industry (*Diffusion NMR of Confined Systems, 2016*), including the food industry (Cobo et al., 2017; Lolli & Caligiani, 2024).

In this work, we show that Fast Field Cycling Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (FFC-NMR), one of the variants of the NMR technique, could be used as a tool to differentiate between cheeses made following different processing technologies.

We show that, using a new FFC-NMR approach, the protons of Fiore Sardo cheeses can be grouped into two populations, characterized by a short and a long NMR relaxation time, respectively. To validate the method, the FFC-NMR data were interpreted using the well-known Model-Free model.

This is a preliminary study, but with this result, we show that the differences between artisanal and industrial cheeses, which supposedly arise from the heat treatment of milk, can be uniquely identified. To the best of our knowledge, this novel approach has never been used before to study food products.

2. Nuclear magnetic resonance

Spectroscopic methods might provide much faster precision testing than many other conventional analytical techniques currently adopted in the dairy sector. These methods include NMR, ESR (Electron Spin Resonance), X-ray, and others. These methods employ the emission or

absorption of electromagnetic radiation. NMR methods, specifically Relaxometry or Time-domain NMR (TD-NMR), have been used to investigate dairy products starting from the 1950s, and since many studies have emerged.

In 1958, Odeblad and Westin used ^1H NMR at 21 MHz to identify components in human milk (Odeblad & Westin, 1958). In 1999, Belloque and Ramos published a review on the NMR technique application in dairy products. The review listed various experiments, from the characterization of milk components to structural changes due to heating and different compositions (Belloque, 1999). In 2009, Yi-Qiao Song, in a review, showed that 2D NMR (T_1 - T_2 and D - T_2) is an especially useful technique to study dairy products (Song, 2009). More recently, some potential applications of NMR to the dairy industry have been suggested, based on literature available and modern dairy processing and quality control related issues (Anedda, 2015). The sensitivity of ^1H relaxation rates to ewe milk pasteurization has been demonstrated through an extended screening over the whole lactation using benchtop TD-NMR (Curti et al., 2020).

Benchtop NMR relaxometry enables rapid measurements using economically affordable, robust, compact benchtop instruments, and in some cases, even portable devices (Ariando et al., 2018). These instruments can be deployed in small control laboratories, production facilities, or directly on production lines. When analysis protocols are tailored to specific products or production processes, the testing can be fully automated, eliminating the need for highly specialized personnel as usually needed in academic research.

For these reasons, usage of NMR for quality control in the industry (*Diffusion NMR of Confined Systems, 2016*), including the food industry (Cobo et al., 2017; Lolli & Caligiani, 2024), is increasingly becoming the method of choice. NMR represents a wide range of phenomena that employ the interaction of low energy electromagnetic radiation (Radio Frequency) with the nucleus of atoms. Low-field TD-NMR is a relatively fast, non-invasive, and inexpensive technique that does not require extensive sample preparation. Almost any material – liquid, solid, colloidal, or complex heterogeneous matrixes – could be investigated as it is. NMR allows one to observe materials' structure, transport, and molecular dynamics in situ.

TD-NMR explores the relaxation time of the atomic nuclei – longitudinal relaxation time T_1 and transverse relaxation time T_2 . The observed relaxation processes are due to the interactions with each other and their environment of the magnetic dipole moment, an intrinsic quantum nuclear property related to the nuclear spin. The nucleus in the molecules is characterized by T_1 and T_2 relaxation time depending on its mobility, which in turn depends on the size and mobility of the molecules.

2.1. Fast field cycling

Most studies that employ NMR to investigate food and dairy specifically use conventional TD-NMR at a fixed magnetization field B_0 . Alternatively, FFC-NMR studies T_1 as a function of the strength of B_0 . Varying the magnetic field strength changes the Larmor frequency and thus the field fluctuations due to the molecular movements, to which the nuclear spin relaxation is sensitive (Kimmich & Anardo, 2004).

Using FFC-NMR, the main interest lies in exploring the correlation time τ_c (the average time a molecule persists in some state of motion) of the magnetic dipolar fluctuation that is influenced by molecular fluctuation and is responsible for T_1 relaxation (Korb, 2017).

The resulting acquired data from such measurements is the so-called NMRD (Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Dispersion) profile (Stelar, 2022).

Having a broad NMRD profile enables the tracing of different molecular dynamics that occur at different time scales. Lower frequencies are related to slower dynamics, such as collective motions and restricted or non-restricted translational self-diffusion. Higher frequencies provide information on faster processes, such as rotations and reorientations of molecules (Kimmich & Anardo, 2004).

FFC-NMR is a relatively fast and non-destructive technique, and therefore, it is an elective technique to investigate the same sample over time.

Here, we present only a brief introduction to the FFC NMR technique. An extended theoretical and technical background of the technique can be found in the paper by Ferrante and Sykora (Ferrante & Sykora, 2005).

In 2015 Steele et al. presented a review of FFC NMR application to different materials, such as rocks, proteins, contrast agents etc. and its future perspectives, including and not limited to FFC MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging), Wide Bore FFC NMR, and 2D NMR correlation spectra with FFC NMR (Steele et al., 2015).

Elif Gokcen Ates et al., 2021, in a review on FFC-NMR in food science, showed that FFC-NMR could be successfully implemented to study molecular dynamics, diffusion, structural changes, food authentication, etc. (Ates et al., 2021).

In 2003, Godefroy et al. studied mozzarella and gouda cheese using FFC-NMR. They observed that protein hydration increases with cheese ripening and determined the degree of protein hydration as a function of aging (Godefroy et al., 2003).

In 2021, using FFC-NMR Anedda et al. observed the differences in the degree of hydration of industrial and artisanal cheeses. They demonstrated that industrial cheeses had a higher degree of hydration and a more disordered distribution of protein protons than artisanal ones (Anedda, Melis and Curti, 2021). In the same year, Conte et al. studied Parmigiano Reggiano cheese using FFC-NMR. They demonstrated that FFC-NMR could be successfully used to study molecular changes in hard cheeses due to aging. It was possible to discriminate between water molecules trapped in casein micelles, water molecules directly bound to the polar groups of the organic moieties, proteins, and fats with different molecular dynamics (Conte et al., 2021).

Several other studies have emerged in the last few years, e.g. FFC-NMR as a technique for quality control and authentication of cheese (Maikowska-Kowalczyk et al., 2024), differentiation among dairy products by a combination of FFC-NMR with other techniques (Piacenza et al., 2022), water fraction exploration in cheeses etc. (Kruk et al., 2021).

The main basic concepts can be found in the famous book of Abragam and Hebel (1961) derived from quantum mechanics observations (Abragam & Hebel, 1961).

2.2. NMRD profile interpretation

To interpret the information from the NMRD profile, a conceptual model is necessary to describe the spin dynamics as a consequence of the interaction with the environment in which they are confined.

In the last decades, many models have been established for NMRD data treatment. Many of them, like Korb, Levitz, or Kimmich models, were established for specific systems (Kimmich & Weber, 1993; Korb, 2011; Levitz, 2005).

Alternatively, the “model-free” (Halle et al., 1998) is a mathematical model that represents NMRD curves as a linear combination of Lorentzian terms, the number of which must be discretionally/empirically set. If the NMRD profile sufficiently covers low- and high-frequency plateaus, it is possible to extract some physical quantities related to molecular dynamics without invoking a specific conceptual model that details the interactions between the nuclei and the environment. The extended theory of the model-free approach could be found in the article by B. Halle, H. Jóhannesson, and K. Venu (Halle et al., 1998).

Previously, similar systems were successfully analyzed by a model-free approach (Conte et al., 2021) and by Korb's model (Anedda, Melis, & Curti, 2021). As our analysis was mostly focused on the component separation as a possible analysis of the NMRD data, we have not explored the implications of the models used and related problems of data inversion (fittings) using ModelFree as a starting point.

Because we are interested in validating the proposed procedure rather than deriving specific parameters, the regression of the NMRD

curves will be done using the model-free.

Quadrupole relaxation (effect on the NMRD profile due to the matching resonance frequencies of the two nuclear species: ^1H and ^{14}N in our case) has been observed in various systems, such as cheeses (Conte et al., 2021), immobilized proteins (Goddard et al., 2009), or tissue (Broche et al., 2011). In this study, we included quadrupolar peaks parameters during the data treatment with a “model-free” approach, as it significantly improved the fitting. But, as we were interested in the separation of the frequency dependent pools of spins, this feature did not show sample dependent frequencies, and QP region was sampled with a limited number of points, we opted not to further analyze QP fitted parameters in this paper.

3. Materials and methods

NMRD profiles were recorded using the Bench-top FFC-NMR Relaxometer (SMARtracer, Stelar S. r.l., Mede, Italy) in the frequency range from 10 MHz to 0.01 MHz. The instrument's acquisition field was set to 7.2 MHz.

The full profile was recorded using Non-Polarized (NP) and Pre-Polarized (PP) sequences with the field's threshold value of 3.5 MHz for changing to the PP sequence. The dead time was 20 μs , the 90° pulse was 8 μs , the recycle delay (RD) was 1 s, and the switching time (SWT) was 3 ms. The T_1 relaxation curves were recorded with 64 logarithmically spaced times from $4 \cdot T_{1\text{MAX}}$ to $0.01 \cdot T_{1\text{MAX}}$ over 512 points, with $T_{1\text{MAX}}$ being evaluated T_1 at each field. The NMRD profile consisted of 32 logarithmically spaced B_R (relaxation fields) acquisitions. The measurements were performed at 27 °C using the built-in temperature controller of the probe VTC90.

Six Fiore Sardo PDO cheese samples were purchased from local producers in Sardinia (Italy): three samples were acquired from the industry (I_1 , I_2 , and I_3) and one from a small artisan producer (A_2). Another sample (A_1) was purchased from a maturer industry, that buys very young (approximately 1 month-ripened) cheese wheels from artisans and ripens them in industrial cellars. All the aforementioned cheeses were ripened for approximately 9 months, according to the claims reported on their label or to the information provided by the seller. One additional cheese wheel was purchased from the industry and left in a ripening cellar for an overall ripening time of approximately 3 years.

Vacuum-sealed samples were kept in the fridge at 4–6 °C until analysis. For the measurements, a small quantity of cheese paste was taken from the middle of the sample, far away from the crust and placed in a glass tube (8 mm in diameter). Samples were kept at room temperature for up to 15 min and then put in the NMR probe.

Usually, the points of an NMRD curve (the relaxation rate $R_1 = 1/T_1$) are obtained by regression with a mono-exponential function of the relaxation curves acquired with the NP/PP sequences that constitute the whole NMRD measurement.

Differently, in this work, the NP/PP curves were processed using UpenWin software (developed by the NMR Unibo team, site.unibo.it/softwareedicam), which implements the UPEN algorithm (Borgia et al., 1998). UPEN performs a uniform-penalty Tikhonov-like locally adapted regularization approach that allows also non-negative constraint. What is obtained by an inversion with UpenWin is a quasi-continuous distribution of relaxation times. The term quasi-continuous refers to the fact that the point on the abscissa is clearly finite, not infinite, generally around 100 values.

The correlation times of the samples were obtained from the NMRD profiles using the ModelFreeFFC software (Bortolotti, Brizi, et al., 2024), developed by the NMR Unibo team and freely distributed (site.unibo.it/softwareedicam).

ModelFreeFFC allows the NMRD curve to be regressed using an interpretative model a linear combination of Lorentzian terms (see part 2) and solves the “ill-posed problem” with l_1 -Regularized Least Squares Problem Solver (Bortolotti, Conte, et al., 2024).

4. Results and discussion

In this part, we demonstrate that NMRD profiles of the artisanal and industrial cheeses can be decomposed into two different components and how this analysis could serve to differentiate between different processing protocols followed in the manufacture of the same PDO cheeses. This information is original and useful for quality control and authentication of PDO hard cheeses. In fact, for successfully safeguarding PDO labels and productions, new and deeper knowledge of the composition, structure, and molecular dynamics of these systems should be attained, which is not accessible through most conventional methods.

As a default initial approach, NMRD profiles of the Fiore Sardo cheeses are shown in Fig. 1, where all R_1 (or T_1) were computed from raw data assuming mono-exponential behavior, as consistently reported for the FFC-NMR analyses of cheeses (Anedda, Pardu, et al., 2021; Conte et al., 2021; Godefroy et al., 2003; Kruk et al., 2021; Małkowska-Kowalczyk et al., 2024).

The first observation from the profiles is that the I_4 sample showed different behavior at lower frequencies than all other samples. This might be likely due to the significant differences in aging, as the I_4 sample was more than 3 years old, while all others were approximately 9 months old. The observation of lower R_1 values at very low fields in aged cheeses with respect to their younger counterparts generally agrees with previous results (Anedda, Melis, & Curti, 2021; Conte et al., 2021; Godefroy et al., 2003). At the lowest frequencies, the I_4 sample showed the smallest R_1 value with respect to all other samples. When decreasing the field from 10 MHz, the I_4 sample overlapped with the A_2 sample up to circa 3 MHz and spread out at lower frequencies, suggesting different motion mechanisms being detected at the high and low frequency regions.

At high frequencies, beyond 1 MHz, the A_1 sample did not differ significantly from the I_{1-3} samples, whereas at lower frequencies the A_1 and A_2 samples seem to be “grouped” from the I_n samples.

At lower frequencies, from about 50 kHz and down, profiles of the samples I_4 and A_2 demonstrated a decrease or plateau. Such decrease or plateau of R_1 at low fields was recorded previously in different samples, such as very-long aged Parmigiano Reggiano PDO (Conte et al., 2021) or biological tissue (Di Gregorio et al., 2019). In their publications, the authors did not focus on this behavior.

In a number of experiments with samples similar to the one investigated in this article, we observed a similar plateau/decrease of R_1 at lower fields (not published data), but we will not specifically focus on this behavior in this paper.

A comparison of the NMRD of Fig. 1 with those previously published for similar or other cheese types (Anedda, Pardu, et al., 2021 on similar cheeses; Conte et al., 2021 on Parmigiano Reggiano; Godefroy et al.,

2003 on Gouda and mozzarella), reveals that I_n samples show the characteristic relaxometry features of cheeses that have undergone longer ripening periods compared to the A_n samples. However, since the ripening time for all samples except I_4 is comparable, this is certainly a result of the processing steps to which industrial products have been subjected.

Previous studies have attributed the decrease in R_1 at the plateau to an increase in cheese protein hydration (Anedda, Pardu, et al., 2021; Godefroy et al., 2003). By analogy, such profiles may also be linked to a hydration effect induced by processing rather than by ripening. Notably, prior research has already suggested that differences between industrial and artisanal cheeses arise from production processes occurring before the aging phase (Anedda, Pardu, et al., 2021). This hypothesis is further supported by the observation that cheese A_1 , which is produced using artisanal methods but aged in industrial cellars, exhibits NMRD profiles more similar to those of the entirely artisanal cheese A_2 than to the industrially produced samples. Considering this, it can be inferred that industrial cheesemaking process leads to an objectively more hydrated state of the protein-fat matrix with respect to the artisanal products.

It should be emphasized here, for those not specialized in NMR relaxometry, that complex molecular systems, such as cheese, intrinsically exhibit molecular mobilities spanning different frequencies. Distinct molecular mobilities coexist simultaneously within the same system, reflecting the intrinsic interactions among the various molecular components. These mobilities significantly influence the macroscopic properties of the cheeses, including consistency, texture, and sensory characteristics. The variation of R_1 with respect to the applied magnetic field in FFC-NMR measurements does not induce changes in the molecular dynamics but rather provides a means to probe them. This technique acts as a “window” into the molecular dynamics, allowing for their observation across a spectrum of frequencies (10 kHz to 10 MHz in our case). The frequency sweep does not stimulate or alter these dynamics, which are inherent to the system, but instead enables their characterization by capturing the mobility at each frequency analyzed.

As far as Fiore Sardo PDO is concerned, a firm, crumbly, and grainy texture is expected in the traditionally manufactured, raw-milk cheeses, with a paste that easily breaks into flakes (Mendia et al., 1999). However, as mentioned above, the use of thermally treated milk in the manufacture of Fiore Sardo PDO has been associated with different visual appearance (Anedda, Pardu, et al., 2021), different NMR relaxometry features (Mulas et al., 2013), and unfair industrial practices (Ledda, 2025; Pittalis et al., 2025; Siniscalchi, 2013; Siniscalchi, 2014). Indeed, milk pasteurization is expected to produce cheeses with a creamier, less grainy texture and higher moisture content than raw milk cheeses, with the differences between raw-milk and pasteurized milk Fiore Sardo supposedly decreasing as the ripening time advances (Mendia et al., 1999; Singh & Waungana, 2001).

The type of milk used for cheesemaking influences the texture and the structure of the cheese matrix. It is possible to explain the changes in the structure of cheese caused by heat treatment of milk through the analysis of the interactions between water and the protein matrix (what is more generally referred to as para-casein hydration state (Guinee, 2015)), of the effects of denaturation of whey proteins (Park et al., 1996; Rynne et al., 2004), and by following mineral equilibria (Singh & Waungana, 2001). However, due to the complexity of the cheese system, the conclusions on such differences in real commercial cheeses, based on conventional analyses, appear to be somewhat inconsistent.

Concerning the microstructure, Morales-Celaya et al. reported that the cheeses made from raw milk presented relatively long and thin casein strands, whereas cheeses from pasteurized milk showed layered casein structure with smaller fat globules. They also reported that cheeses from raw milk have lower protein and moisture content (Morales-Celaya et al., 2011). A more open structure and numerous irregular cavities were observed in pasteurized milk goats' milk cheese compared to more regular and close protein matrix in raw milk cheese (Buffa et al., 2001).

Fig. 1. NMRD profiles of the Pecorino DOP cheeses.

Studies of the effect of the heat treatment of milk have been also carried out on traditional cheeses such as Manchego and Cheddar. [Gaya et al. \(1990\)](#) found that Manchego cheese made from raw ewe's milk showed lower fracturability, elasticity and hardness than that made of pasteurized milk. Such differences in textural characteristics could be confirmed for long ripened Manchego cheese only by [Gomez et al. \(1999\)](#). These properties were attributed to the level of moisture and water-soluble nitrogen (WSN): as the casein is more intact with lower moisture content, fracturability and deformability are lower. However, Manchego cheese made from raw milk showed higher values of friability, graininess, roughness, and hardness than their counterparts manufactured from pasteurized milk, which paste resulted more elastic, cohesive, and containing higher moisture ([Viñas et al., 2007](#)). The microstructure of the raw milk cheeses was found to be more uniform with smaller and more regular fat globules ([Beuvier & Buchin, 2004](#)). Cheddar cheese produced from raw milk cheese was found to present a crumblier texture than the pasteurized milk cheese, which on the contrary was significantly characterized by a rubbery consistency ([Rehman](#)

[et al., 2000](#)).

Other NMR relaxometry features can be very informative about the state of the cheese paste and the association between them and the cheesemaking processing. For example, all cheese samples around 2 MHz showed so-called quadrupolar peaks (QP). However, since the investigation was focused on a more general scope, in this preliminary analysis, this region was sampled with only a limited number of points, which resulted in a loose profiling of the QP.

Aiming to more deeply characterize water-paracasein interactions and dynamics, using UpenWin software, we processed the magnetization decay curves at each NMRD profile point to get quasi-continuous distributions of T_1 (or R_1) values. For every sample we identified two components in the low field region (Fig. 2), which we refer to as the “short” and “long” components, corresponding to short T_1 and long T_1 , respectively. This observation is very original with respect to both the information made accessible by conventional analytical methods and with respect to previous findings based on the application to the FFC-NMR characterization of cheeses. As it will be detailed in the

Sample A_2

Sample I_3

Fig. 2. Quasi-continuous T_1 distribution of A_2 and I_3 samples through different NMRD profile points.

following, this observation can provide new and important information on the “state” of the caseous matrix and on the interaction between key molecular components such as proteins and water in cheese.

Fig. 2 shows the T_1 quasi-continuous distribution of each NMRD point of samples A_2 and I_3 , taken as representative examples of the artisanal and industrial Fiore Sardo cheeses. The T_1 distribution of the other samples can be found in the supplementary material (S1).

For both samples in Fig. 2, when field decreases from 10 MHz down to around 2 MHz, the mono-modal distribution represents the “average” T_1 time, suggesting that at a higher field, both components are coalesced. This highlights a key advantage of FFC-NMR over fixed-field TD-NMR, as its ability to distinguish between the two components provides novel insights into cheese dynamics that are not accessible at magnetic fields above approximately 2 MHz. For lower fields than about 2 MHz, biexponential decay likely arises from slow exchange, in the time scale of the NMR experiment, between the two dynamically coupled pools of protons, namely the solid protein network and liquid water protons. In fact, nuclear spin-lattice relaxation in hydrated protein systems such as cheese can be represented by two spin (hydrogen) populations coupled by magnetization exchange. Each pool can be described with a single relaxation rate R_1 , since sufficient mixing occurs via fast spin diffusion in the solid para-casein matrix and by fast exchange and translational diffusion in the liquid water (Bryant & Shirley, 1980a, 1980b; Lester & Bryant, 1991). At some points (frequencies), we also discovered a third component of around 3 ms, but as it was not consistently present and considering the minimum T_1 time accessible by the technique, we did not include this component in our analysis.

The presence of different proton pools does not necessarily involve the presence of different sites or chemical species but must be interpreted as the result of different interactions of diffusion, morphology, and relaxation rates within the sample (Hills et al., 1990). Fig. 3 displays the NMRDs of long and short T_1 components separately for each sample.

Despite the data being scattered, some characteristic features of the samples can be extrapolated. In the future, more careful measurements with more scans and points of the frequencies in the QP region and in the T_1 relaxation curves are needed to increase the signal-to-noise ratio and to improve the accuracy of the data inversion as the quadrature peaks are almost confused with noise.

Considering the long T_1 component, we did not see considerable characteristic patterns of industrial and artisanal cheeses, all the samples showing quite similar contribution to the overall NMRD profile of Fig. 1. Here, R_1 appeared to decline in the lower fields for I_4 , and was smaller than other samples. This might suggest that aging time was the main discrimination factor for a long component. The I_1 sample showed similar behavior. The A_1 sample showed the highest R_1 value. However, data appears quite scattered and does not allow drawing a conclusive picture.

The short T_1 component demonstrated similar patterns to the overall NMRD profiles shown in Fig. 1, with the A_2 sample having the highest R_1 value, I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 the lowest, and A_1 falling at an intermediate level. For the short component, I_4 was closer to A_2 , which suggests that artisanal cheese and long-aged industrial cheese had similar molecular dynamics of the short component. The scattering of the lowest field points in the short component of I_4 might have resulted from the reduced number of experimental scans in the quite fast acquisition protocol used. The similarity between results obtained for the very-long ripened I_4 and A_2 well agrees with the expected slower ripening of industrial cheeses, likely related to the effect of excessive heat treatments of the cheese components (Singh & Waungana, 2001).

Both components exhibited peaks in the 2.6–2.1 MHz Larmor frequency region, which might indicate quadrupolar peaks. But as the profiles of two separated components were scattered, more experiments are needed to corroborate these results.

The macroscopic texture and sensory characteristics of cheese are greatly influenced by water and water-protein interactions. Moreover, water plays a key role in promoting and regulating hydrolysis and proteolysis of cheese proteins, which are fundamental processes for the development of the desired texture, appearance, aroma, and flavor of many cheeses over ripening time, as discussed in previous studies (Farkye, Kiely, Allshouse, & Kindstedt, 1991; Fox, 1989; Lawrence, Creamer, & Gilles, 1987). As suggested by the NMR relaxometry data presented here, water in cheese exists in distinct pools with different degrees of water molecule mobility: some are relatively free, though confined; others are located near or within fat globules, and its mobility is reduced; and some are bound to proteins, particularly caseins. It is of significant interest to reflect on and understand how the balance between these different water pools may influence the macroscopic sensory characteristics of cheese. Furthermore, optimizing analytical tools and protocols that enable a non-destructive, rapid, and cost-effective evaluation of the quantitative and qualitative relationship between these water pools represents a notable competitive advantage for the dairy industry and its associated sectors.

It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the amount of NMR signal of each component (proportional to the area under the peaks) changed as the relaxation field decreased. Changes in the percentage of two components through the relaxation field points are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 plots the percentage area under the peaks relative to the short (orange dots) and long (blue dots) T_1 components for different field values. The regression lines show opposite trends for the long and short T_1 components across all samples (A_1 , A_2 , I_1 – I_4). The short component shows an increasing trend with increasing Larmor frequency, while the long T_1 component has a decreasing trend. At higher relaxation fields, faster processes are more visible and slower processes less visible. In samples A_2 and I_4 , the components intersect at approximately 1 MHz

Fig. 3. NMRD profiles for all samples obtained from the separation of long T_1 (on the left) and short T_1 (on the right) components.

Fig. 4. Percentage evolution of the signal amount of long and short T_1 components as a function of larmor frequency.

Larmor frequency, with each component representing about 50 % of the total signal at this point.

For all samples, the percentage ratio of long T_1 and short T_1 components at higher fields was about 30:70 respectively. As the field decreased for samples I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 the percentage ratio almost stabilized to about 50:50, whereas for samples A_2 and I_4 it reversed to 70:30. For sample A_1 it changed to an intermediate value of 60:40. As at higher relaxation fields faster processes are more visible, such as the rotational motion of molecules, this might suggest that artisanal and industrial cheeses have similar molecular dynamic for the motions described by smaller correlation time.

Lower frequencies are related to slower molecular motions, such as collective molecular movement and diffusion. As a first general consideration, these differences in the percentage ratios at the lower fields might suggest that slower molecular dynamics are different between I_n and A_n samples. A deeper analysis of the acquired NMRD shows R_1 exhibit a power-law dependence on Larmor frequency, initially increasing before plateauing at lower frequencies. Different models have been used for interpreting and fitting such NMRD in aged cheeses

(Anedda, Melis, & Curti, 2021; Conte et al., 2021; Godefroy et al., 2003; Piacenza et al., 2022). Among them, this behavior is consistent with models used for hydrated proteins (Korb & Bryant, 2001; Lester & Bryant, 1991) and suggests a relationship between the relaxation rate and protein hydration. As cheese ripens, the protein hydration level increases, resulting in a lower relaxation rate plateau at low frequency. Therefore, in solid hydrated protein matrixes like cheeses, the plateau at low frequencies reflects the influence of hydration, while the relaxation rates approach a limit defined by confined free water at high frequencies, which lacks this frequency dispersion due to faster molecular motions.

Sample I_4 was an industrial sample, aged for longer than 3 years. Its percentage ratio was almost identical to the A_2 (artisanal sample). This could be explained in terms of the faster ripening of the artisanal cheese and considering the hydration state of the protein matrix in the two samples (Anedda, Pardu, et al., 2021). However, in industrial I_4 , such hydration state has been reached after 3 years of ripening, while artisan product A_2 reached the same state of ripening after 9 months. This also agrees with previous studies on the evolution of the sensory

characteristics of Fiore Sardo PDO, which demonstrated that as ripening time advanced, the differences between the cheeses made from raw milk and pasteurized milk decreased (Mendia et al., 1999).

At higher fields, the short T_1 component is predominant for all the samples, suggesting that faster molecular dynamic is dominant, likely associated with the free water molecules (though characterized by much slower dynamics than bulk water), in the cheese matrix (Kruk et al., 2021). But for samples A_2 , I_4 , and partially A_1 the long component was visibly more important at lower fields, which suggests that a slower molecular dynamic dominated the relaxation. In samples I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 the percentage ratio was 50:50 for the long and short components at lower fields.

In fact, in samples I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 the two components achieve an effective balance in the low field region. It is evident that neither the more rigid fraction, characterized by slower mobilities, nor the more fluid fraction, exhibiting faster mobilities, dominates in determining the overall relaxation rate. In this context, it seems that in industrial cheese samples, the state of protein hydration ensures faster mobility even at low fields, ultimately contributing to the well-known creaminess and rubbery features of the texture. A reasonable explanation for the observed data is that in hard cheeses water is distributed into two distinct pools, each exhibiting different NMR relaxometry characteristics. The quantitative distribution of these pools is likely determined by the cheesemaking process, including milk treatments, aging conditions and duration, all of which ultimately affect the molecular mobility of the constituents that form the product.

To further examine the molecular dynamics of the studied systems, we interpreted the profiles using a model-free approach. As an example of the fitting, Fig. 5 displays the experimental profiles and fitted curves of two samples.

Despite the acquisition of the NMRD being carried out with a limited number of points in the region typical for quadrature peaks, fitting was done including quadrupolar peaks as statistical results appeared to be better with QP than without. As correlation times found by the model-free approach cannot be directly attributed to the specific components of the system, we opted to demonstrate the weighted average correlation time of the samples. The exact correlation times from the model-free fitting could be found in the Supplementary material (S2).

The average correlation time $\langle \tau_c \rangle$ of the I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 samples appeared to be longer than that of the A_n samples and I_4 samples and are in the range of 0.06–0.14 μs . The difference between samples is narrow. We fitted the NMRD profiles of the short T_1 components, as the one showing discrimination between milk treatment separately to account for its molecular dynamics.

Table 1 shows the correlation times from the model-free fitting with the short T_1 component. Due to the high scattering of the curves and the

Table 1

Average weighted correlation times from the model-free fitting of all samples.

Sample	Average weighted correlation time, $\langle \tau_c \rangle$ in μs
A_1	0.4
A_2	0.2
I_1	0.6
I_2	0.5
I_3	0.7
I_4	0.1

few points acquired in the region 1.8–3.5 MHz, quadrupolar peaks were excluded.

Assuming, as a mere speculative exercise, that Model-free is an appropriate interpretative model, then for both components, the average correlation time of A_2 and I_4 samples are the smallest, with I_4 having the shortest correlation time among all samples.

Shorter correlation times indicate smaller molecular size, which further supports the theory of protein denaturation of raw milk cheeses happening faster than in pasteurized milk cheeses and matching with long aged cheese. This result provides complementary and deeper information on Fiore Sardo ripening with respect to the conventional analyses of ripening indexes (Pirisi et al., 1999). Moreover, the correlation time of the I_4 (3-year-old cheese) is the smallest for both components, indicating the highest degree of maturation in terms of the effect of proteolysis and deriving average molecular size.

5. Conclusion

In this work, we showed the NMRD profiles of 6 PDO Pecorino cheese samples, two (A_n) being artisanal cheeses, and 4 (I_n) being industrial cheeses. We observed two clearly separated components through the NMRD profiles for each sample, with separation being more pronounced at lower fields. Whereas at higher fields these two components tend to merge.

Particularly, we showed that artisanal cheeses had shorter T_1 values at lower fields than industrial cheeses. Longer T_1 values indicate that the industrial cheeses had more moisture.

This suggests that the exploration of the NMR signal at lower fields might provide additional information on the structure and dynamics of dairy products.

We dubbed components as short and long, indicating components with fast and slow mobility, respectively. At first approximation, the dynamics of the two components were the result of different protein hydration and molecular sizes, in turn reflecting the effects of ripening in differently processed milk and cheese during the cheesemaking process of Fiore Sardo.

Fig. 5. Model-free fitting of the A_2 sample profile (on the left) and the I_3 sample (on the right).

We were able to observe the changes in the signal amount of each component through the relaxation fields. Each sample showed a similar percentage ratio of two components at higher fields of 30:70 for long and short T_1 components, respectively, suggesting similar molecular dynamics for industrial and artisanal products at higher fields. At lower fields, for A_2 and I_4 samples, the percentage ratio changed to 70:30, whereas for I_1 , I_2 , and I_3 two components showed a 50:50 ratio. Sample A_1 showed intermediate values of 40:60 at lower fields. This suggests different slower molecular dynamics between artisanal and industrial components, predominantly due to the moisture content differences. Since A_1 cheese is an artisanal product that has been ripened in industrial cellars by a maturer industry, the evidence of intermediate behavior suggests a subtle, but detectable, role of ripening condition to the relaxometry features detected by FFC-NMR. Judging by the separated NMRD profiles, the short T_1 component was more sensitive to the artisanal-industrial cheese differences, whereas long T_1 component distributions were more scattered.

Analysis of the NMRD profiles by model-free model revealed that the artisanal samples and long aged sample (I_4) had the fastest dynamics concerning the NMRD profiles, treated as mono-exponential, and short component with I_4 being the fastest, which suggests protein degradation, as molecules get smaller, resulting in faster dynamics.

We hypothesized, also based on previous results, that the discrimination by FFC-NMR technique of our samples comes predominantly from the thermal treatment of milk proteins, despite many other parameters influencing cheese's structure.

These findings not only show that the FFC-NMR technique could be used to discriminate between different processing treatments in cheeses and, most importantly, provide a first detailed exploration of two components of cheese and their molecular dynamics through NMRD profiles.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Anastasiia Nagmutdinova: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Leonardo Brizi:** Software. **Villiam Bortolotti:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Gianni Ferrante:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration. **Fabiana Zama:** Software, Methodology. **Germana Landi:** Software, Methodology. **Roberto Anedda:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2025.116679>.

Data availability

We have shared the link to the data <https://rci-get.uwm.edu.pl/s/jsFYjs4Tz85LP2S>.

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